

The Role of Product Innovation on Purchasing Decisions with Iconic Ethnical Products as a Mediating Variable among Pamekasan Batik Artisans

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to examine the role of product innovation in influencing purchasing decisions with iconic ethnical product as a mediating variable among consumers of Pamekasan batik. Using a quantitative approach, data were collected through a structured questionnaire distributed to Pamekasan batik consumers. The data were analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) to test both direct and indirect relationships among variables. The results indicate that product innovation has a significant positive effect on iconic ethnical product, but does not directly influence purchasing decisions. In contrast, iconic ethnical product has a significant positive effect on purchasing decisions and plays a mediating role in the relationship between product innovation and purchasing decisions. These findings suggest that product innovation contributes to purchasing decisions only when it strengthens the iconic and ethnical characteristics of the product, such as cultural symbolism, distinctive motifs, and local identity. The study highlights that consumers of Pamekasan batik place greater emphasis on symbolic value and cultural meaning rather than product novelty alone. The results support Consumer Culture Theory, emphasizing that purchasing decisions for cultural products are shaped by culturally constructed meanings. Practically, this study implies that Pamekasan batik artisans should orient product innovation strategies toward reinforcing iconic ethnical values to enhance consumer purchasing decisions.

KEYWORDS: Batik, Consumer Culture, Product Innovation, Iconic Ethnical Product, Purchasing Decision.

I. INTRODUCTION

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) are one of the main driving forces of Indonesia's economy. According to Law Number 20 of 2008, micro enterprises are defined as productive businesses owned by individuals or individual business entities. Small enterprises are independent productive economic businesses operated by individuals or business entities that are neither subsidiaries nor branches of companies owned, controlled by, or directly or indirectly affiliated with medium or large enterprises. Medium enterprises are independent productive economic businesses operated by individuals or business entities that are neither subsidiaries nor branches of companies owned, controlled by, or directly or indirectly affiliated with small or large enterprises. The criteria for Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs)

Table 1. MSME Criteria

Business Category	Capital (IDR)	Annual Sales Turnover (IDR)
Micro Enterprise	≤ 50 million	≤ 300 million
Small Enterprise	> 50 million – 500 million	> 300 million – ≤ 2,500 million
Medium Enterprise	> 500 million – 10,000 million	> 2,500 million – ≤ 50,000 million

Source: Law of the Republic of Indonesia (2008)

MSMEs are one of the key sectors driving national economic growth, particularly in creating employment opportunities and improving community welfare at the local level (Ramadhani & Raharjo, 2023). Along with Indonesia's increasingly rapid economic development, MSMEs continue to demonstrate their strategic contribution, despite facing various challenges such as limited capital, restricted access to technology, and difficulties in reaching broader markets. One of the main obstacles frequently encountered is the lack of understanding among MSME actors in developing innovative products and implementing appropriate marketing strategies

(Ardiansyah & Nur, 2023). Nevertheless, MSMEs have proven to be highly resilient to economic crises. During the economic recession caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, for example, more than half of MSME actors were able to survive by adjusting their business models and leveraging available assets, including the strength of social networks (Mardanugraha & Junaidi, 2022). This is consistent with the findings of Qolby (2025), which emphasize that adaptation to digital technology is a crucial factor in maintaining business sustainability amid economic pressure.

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in Indonesia make a substantial contribution to the national Gross Domestic Product (GDP). In 2024, Indonesian MSMEs contributed approximately IDR 9,500 trillion to the country’s GDP at current prices. With Indonesia’s GDP in 2024 estimated at around IDR 15,573 trillion, MSMEs accounted for approximately 61% of total GDP. In addition, MSMEs employed around 117 million people, representing about 97% of the total workforce in Indonesia (including MSMEs and large enterprises). Currently, Indonesia records approximately 66 million MSME units, accounting for 99.9% of the total business units nationwide (Ministry of Cooperatives and MSMEs, 2024). East Java Province is one of the largest regions in Indonesia; therefore, it is not surprising that this province makes a significant contribution to the national economy. In 2024, 25.07% of Java Island’s Gross Domestic Product (GDP) originated from East Java’s Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP). The Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprise (MSME) sector serves as the backbone of the regional economy. This is reflected in the performance of the manufacturing sector over recent years, which in 2024 contributed 31.42% to East Java’s total GRDP. Furthermore, the 2024 performance report of the East Java Office of Cooperatives and MSMEs indicates that MSMEs contributed approximately 59% to the province’s GRDP, derived from a total of about 9.86 million business units distributed across the province. According to data from Statistics Indonesia (BPS), East Java’s total GRDP in 2024 was estimated to exceed IDR 2,500 trillion. Although the number of MSMEs in East Java is very large, this study focuses specifically on batik MSMEs located in Pamekasan Regency on Madura Island. This regency has designated Klampar Village in Proppo District as a batik village. Pamekasan is also recognized as the only region producing hand-drawn batik characterized by a dominance of red and brown colors. Currently, the number of batik artisans in Pamekasan is estimated to reach approximately 6,000 individuals. According to data from the Department of Industry and Trade of Pamekasan Regency, there are 933 MSME units of batik artisans spread across the region. Consequently, since 2009, Pamekasan Regency has been officially designated as a batik center in East Java. Previously, the Indonesian World Records Museum (MURI) also acknowledged Pamekasan’s achievement as a region capable of producing hand-drawn batik measuring up to 1,530 meters in length (Damayanti & Zakik, 2023).

Table 2. Volume and Sales Value of Batik in Pamekasan

Year	Volume (pieces)	Sales Value (IDR)
2020	904,662	99,315,462,000
2021	700,873	89,221,132,900
2022	691,898	88,424,564,400
2023	696,673	89,104,476,900
2024	558,317	82,949,598,646

Source: Law of the Republic of Indonesia (2008)

Table 1.2 shows that the volume and value of batik sales in Pamekasan have experienced fluctuating conditions with a generally downward trend. In 2020, batik production volume reached 904,662 pieces, then declined in 2021 to 700,873 pieces. In 2022, the volume further decreased to 691,898 pieces. In 2023, batik volume slightly increased to 696,673 pieces, but then experienced a very significant decline over the last five years, reaching only 558,317 pieces in 2024. According to the Department of Industry and Trade of Pamekasan Regency, Madura, this unstable condition is influenced by the economic crisis, increases in fuel prices, and the lack of innovation and market development among MSMEs.

A company is established to achieve certain objectives by involving many stakeholders. To obtain optimal and sustainable profits so that the company can survive and provide benefits to both owners and employees, the company is required to be able to compete with competitors while maintaining its existing advantages. Therefore, company management must be able to create effective and strategic marketing performance as an effort to achieve such competitive advantage.

The existence of the Pamekasan batik industry must continue to be preserved, considering that batik is one of Indonesia's cultural heritages that was designated by UNESCO in 2009 as an icon of Indonesia. Batik must be managed and sustained as a cultural heritage. Companies operating in the batik industry must continue to be encouraged to develop superior performance. MSMEs that strive to continuously improve their performance should not only focus on competitive advantage but also pay attention to other factors that may influence purchasing decisions.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Diffusion of Innovation Theory

The diffusion of innovation theory was first introduced by Everett M. Rogers in 1962 in his book *Diffusion of Innovations*. This theory seeks to explain how an innovation or a new idea spreads (diffuses) throughout society, either through market channels, non-market channels, or inter-firm interactions (Lee, 2024). However, the early roots of innovation diffusion studies can be traced back to mass communication research by Wang et al. (2021). Their study indicates that mass media and opinion leaders play an important role in influencing society to adopt new ideas or inventions. Accordingly, innovations disseminated through media and community leaders tend to be adopted more rapidly by the public. Etymologically, diffusion refers to the spread of culture, technology, or ideas from one party to another, while innovation refers to a new invention that differs from what previously existed, whether in the form of ideas, methods, or tools. When combined, innovation diffusion can be understood as the process by which new inventions are spread from one party to another within a social system. According to Lee (2024), diffusion is the process by which an innovation is communicated through certain channels over a period of time among members of a social system. Innovation itself is viewed as an idea, practice, or object that is perceived as new by an individual or a particular group.

Product Innovation

According to Kotler and Armstrong, a product is anything that can be offered to the market to attract attention, be used, or be consumed in order to satisfy consumers' needs and wants (Susanto & Cahyono, 2021). Kotler defines product innovation as a combination of various interrelated processes that influence one another. Thus, innovation is not merely a concept of a new idea or invention, nor is it simply the introduction of a new market development; rather, innovation represents an overall depiction of all these interconnected processes (Soekesi et al., 2024). Product innovation refers to a company's capability to manage design processes, research and development, managerial activities, and marketing efforts in order to improve product quality (Zghoul & Al-Haddad, 2021). Tjiptono (2023) states that innovation is the actual implementation of an idea into a new product or process. Innovation may originate from individuals, organizations, or research outcomes. The decision-making process regarding innovation involves searching for and processing information to reduce uncertainty related to the benefits and risks that may arise. The purpose of innovation is to maintain a company's existence amid changing consumer preferences, technological advancements, increasingly shorter product life cycles, and intense market competition.

Purchase Decision

A purchase decision is a series of processes that begins when consumers recognize a problem, search for information about a particular product or brand, and evaluate how well each alternative can solve the problem, ultimately leading to a purchase decision (Tjiptono, 2023). According to Kotler, an individual's intention to purchase a product is not a fully reliable predictor of actual purchasing behavior. Two main elements involved in the purchasing process are purchase intention and the purchase decision itself (Purwanto, 2017). According to Kotler and Armstrong, a purchase decision is a stage in the decision-making process in which consumers actually buy a product (Alamsyah & Cahyono, 2021). In line with this, Ariescy emphasizes that a purchase decision is an individual activity that directly involves decision-making to buy a product offered by a seller (Rahma et al., 2025). A purchase decision can be understood as the stages a person goes through in making a decision, accompanied by actual actions to evaluate, acquire, use, and dispose of a good or service (Efendi & Aminah, 2023). Simply put, a purchase decision is the process by which consumers identify needs or problems, search for relevant product information, consider several alternatives as solutions, and then select the best alternative before finally deciding to make a purchase (Pakan & Purwanto, 2022).

Iconic Ethnical Product

Product competitive advantage refers to the superiority or differentiation of a product compared to competitors' offerings (Al-Abdallah & Al-Salim, 2021). The elements of product advantage include uniqueness, value, and benefits offered by the company

from the customer’s perspective. Sulisiyani and Hutomo (2021) argue that product uniqueness is an important attribute of competitive advantage, influenced by a high level of innovativeness and advanced technology, enabling the creation of products that align with consumer preferences. Iconic product advantage refers to a company’s superiority achieved by creating products that serve as icons or symbols, becoming memorable cues for consumers through the symbols embedded in the product. An icon is a symbol that has a resemblance in form and is easily recognized by its users. In iconic relationships, the connection between the representamen and its object is realized through similarity in qualities. An iconic model represents a physical imitation that resembles the original appearance but on a smaller scale.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework for this study is as follows, based on the review that was received

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

III. METHODOLOGY

This study employed a quantitative research design grounded in the positivist paradigm to examine the influence of product innovation capability and iconic ethnical products on purchase decisions. The research was conducted in Pamekasan Regency, East Java, a major center of the batik industry, from September to November 2025. The population comprised consumers who purchased Pamekasan batik in the region, with the sample consisting of consumers who had made at least one batik purchase within the past three months. A convenience sampling technique was applied, and the sample size was determined using Slovin’s formula with a 10% margin of error, resulting in 100 respondents. Primary data were collected through structured questionnaires, while secondary data were obtained from relevant literature. Data analysis involved descriptive statistics to describe respondent characteristics and variable distributions, as well as inferential analysis using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with AMOS 23. SEM was selected for its ability to simultaneously assess relationships among multiple variables through regression weight analysis and confirmatory factor analysis, enabling both hypothesis testing and construct validation.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The object of this study consists of consumers of Pamekasan batik who have made at least one batik purchase within the last three months. The selection of consumers as the research object is based on the objective of the study, which is to analyze the effect of product innovation on purchase decisions, with iconic ethnical product as a mediating variable. Therefore, respondents who have actual purchasing experience are considered capable of providing more relevant and accurate evaluations of Pamekasan batik products. The profile of Pamekasan batik consumers is presented in Table 3 based on gender and purchase frequency over the past three months.

Table 3. Profile of Pamekasan Batik Consumers

Profile	Category	Frequency (Respondents)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	73	54.89
	Female	60	45.11
Purchase Frequency	Once	54	40.60
	Twice	44	33.08
	Three times	10	7.52
	> Three times	25	18.80
Total		133	100.00

Source: Research Questionnaire

Table 3 shows that the total number of respondents who are consumers of Pamekasan batik is 133 people, with the majority being male, totaling 73 respondents (54.89%). In addition, most respondents reported purchasing Pamekasan batik once within the last three months, amounting to 54 respondents (40.60%).

Table 4. Mahalanobis d-Squared

Observation number	Mahalanobis d-squared	p1	p2
70	60.101	.000	.000
105	59.594	.000	.000
44	57.861	.000	.000
2	49.589	.000	.000
5	48.122	.000	.000
...
45	5.928	.949	1.000
86	5.785	.954	1.000
69	5.415	.965	1.000
10	5.294	.968	1.000
26	5.277	.969	1.000

Source: AMOS 2026

The highest Mahalanobis d-squared value shown in the table is 60.101, which is lower than the Chi-square table value (201.272). Therefore, from a multivariate perspective, no observations were identified as outliers in this study.

Table 5. Assessment of Normality

Variable	min	Max	skew	c.r.	kurtosis	c.r.
IEP1	1.000	5.000	-1.268	-5.970	1.900	4.472
IEP2	1.000	5.000	-2.209	-10.401	7.555	17.785
IEP3	1.000	5.000	-.717	-3.378	-.424	-.997
IEP4	1.000	5.000	-1.680	-7.911	5.190	12.218
IEP5	1.000	5.000	-2.039	-9.598	8.367	19.697
KP4	1.000	5.000	-2.091	-9.845	6.451	15.186
KP3	1.000	5.000	-1.934	-9.104	5.361	12.621
KP2	1.000	5.000	-1.016	-4.783	.086	.203
KP1	1.000	5.000	-1.835	-8.640	4.566	10.748

Variable	min	Max	skew	c.r.	kurtosis	c.r.
IP4	1.000	5.000	-.494	-2.328	-.915	-2.154
IP3	1.000	5.000	-1.203	-5.663	2.155	5.074
IP2	1.000	5.000	-1.729	-8.142	4.665	10.981
IP1	1.000	5.000	-1.824	-8.589	3.748	8.823
Multivariate					111.448	32.541

Source: AMOS 2026

The normality test was conducted by comparing the critical ratio (CR) values in the assessment of normality with the critical value of ± 2.58 . If the multivariate CR value falls within the range of ± 2.58 , the data are considered to meet the normality assumption. Table 5 shows that the multivariate CR value does not fall within the range of ± 2.58 , indicating that the data are not normally distributed on a multivariate basis. Furthermore, univariate normality was assessed by examining the CR values for skewness and kurtosis for each indicator. Based on the output, not all CR values for skewness and kurtosis fall within the range of ± 2.58 , suggesting that the data are also not normally distributed at the univariate level. Despite these results, the use of this data remains acceptable because the study employs a Likert scale and a sample size of ≥ 100 , making the Maximum Likelihood estimation robust to violations of normality. Therefore, the analysis was continued.

Table 6. Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

Variable	Indicator	Loading Factor	Error	Construct Reliability
Product Innovation (IP)	IP1	0.843	0.241	0.705
	IP2	0.842	0.188	
	IP3	0.712	0.389	
	IP4	-0.009	1.573	
Purchase Decision (KP)	KP1	0.734	0.336	0.764
	KP2	0.201	1.427	
	KP3	0.765	0.285	
	KP4	0.931	0.086	
Iconic Ethnical Product (IEP)	IEP1	0.767	0.182	0.801
	IEP2	0.755	0.252	
	IEP3	0.145	1.464	
	IEP4	0.767	0.208	
	IEP5	0.717	0.366	

Source: AMOS 2026

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) was employed to assess the validity of indicators measuring each construct, where an indicator is considered valid if its standardized loading factor exceeds 0.50. The results show that for the Product Innovation (IP) construct, indicators IP1, IP2, IP3, and IP4 have loading factors of 0.843, 0.842, 0.712, and -0.009 , respectively, indicating that IP4 is invalid and should be eliminated from the measurement model. For the Purchase Decision (KP) construct, indicators KP1, KP2, KP3, and KP4 exhibit loading factors of 0.734, 0.201, 0.765, and 0.931, respectively, revealing that KP2 does not meet the validity criterion and therefore needs to be removed. Furthermore, for the Iconic Ethnical Product (IEP) construct, indicators IEP1, IEP2, IEP3, IEP4, and IEP5 show loading factors of 0.767, 0.755, 0.145, 0.767, and 0.717, respectively, indicating that IEP3 is invalid and should be eliminated. Overall, the removal of these invalid indicators improves the accuracy of the measurement model and ensures that all constructs meet the validity requirements in CFA analysis.

Table 7. Goodness of Fit of the Initial Structural Model

Goodness of Fit Index	Cut-off Value	Model Result	Evaluation
Probability	≥ 0.05	0.000	Poor Fit
RMSEA	≤ 0.08	0.130	Poor Fit
GFI	≥ 0.90	0.802	Poor Fit
AGFI	≥ 0.90	0.709	Poor Fit
CMIN/DF	≤ 2.00	3.246	Marginal
TLI	≥ 0.90	0.804	Poor Fit
CFI	≥ 0.90	0.844	Poor Fit

Source: AMOS 2026

Table 7 indicates that none of the Goodness of Fit criteria meet the required cut-off values; therefore, the structural model needed to be modified in the subsequent stage.

Table 8. Goodness of Fit of the Initial Structural Model

Goodness of Fit Index	Cut-off Value	Model Result	Evaluation
Probability	≥ 0.05	0.002	Poor Fit
RMSEA	≤ 0.08	0.081	Good Fit
GFI	≥ 0.90	0.916	Good Fit
AGFI	≥ 0.90	0.855	Marginal
CMIN/DF	≤ 2.00	1.827	Good Fit
TLI	≥ 0.90	0.949	Good Fit
CFI	≥ 0.90	0.964	Good Fit

Source: AMOS 2026

After model modification, the Goodness of Fit indices obtained are presented in Table 8

Table 9. Hypothesis Result

Hypothesis	Path	Coefficient	S.E.	C.R.	p-value	Interpretation
H1	Product Innovation (IP) → Iconic Ethnical Product (IEP)	0.529	0.069	7.704	0.000	Positive, Significant
H2	Product Innovation (IP) → Purchase Decision (KP)	0.035	0.112	0.315	0.753	Positive, Insignificant
H3	Iconic Ethnical Product (IEP) → Purchase Decision (KP)	1.076	0.208	5.181	0.000	Positive, Significant

Source: AMOS 2026

The Effect of Product Innovation on Iconic Ethnical Product

The results confirm that product innovation has a significant positive effect on iconic ethnical product, indicating that the ability of Pamekasan batik artisans to innovate plays a crucial role in strengthening the ethnic identity and cultural distinctiveness of their products. Innovations in design, production techniques, product development, and packaging enhance product differentiation, aesthetic value, and symbolic meaning, making Pamekasan batik more easily recognized as an iconic ethnic product. Consumers generally perceive both product innovation and iconic ethnical product characteristics positively, particularly in terms of design changes, technical innovation, symbolic appeal, and motif superiority. These findings support Consumer Culture Theory, which emphasizes the role of product innovation in shaping culturally constructed meanings and consumer experiences (Sabbar et al.,

2023), and are consistent with Nuraeni et al. (2025), who argue that innovation in design, function, and technology strengthens product iconography.

The Effect of Product Innovation on Purchase Decision

The results indicate that product innovation does not have a significant effect on purchase decision, suggesting that improvements in design, motifs, colors, and production techniques of Pamekasan batik do not directly determine consumers' purchasing decisions. Although consumers generally perceive product innovation and purchase decision positively, innovation is not the primary consideration in deciding to purchase Pamekasan batik. Purchase decisions tend to be more strongly influenced by emotional factors and symbolic values, such as cultural relevance, identity attachment, price sensitivity, and perceived traditional quality. This finding is consistent with Mavilinda and Susanti (2022), who argue that product innovation may not always provide added value for consumers, and with Consumer Culture Theory, which views purchase decisions as being shaped more by culturally constructed meanings and consumption experiences than by product innovation alone (Sabbar et al., 2023). Thus, product innovation functions more as a supporting factor that enhances product appeal rather than as a direct determinant of consumers' purchase decisions.

The Effect of Job Insecurity on Turnover Intention

Job insecurity was found to have a significant positive effect on turnover intention. Indicating that higher job insecurity leads to greater turnover intention. Employees who perceive their jobs as highly valuable may view the potential loss of employment as a serious threat, generating anxiety that drives them to seek alternative opportunities. Conversely, when employees feel secure through clear contracts, transparent communication, and stable career paths, their anxiety is reduced, allowing them to remain focused and less inclined to leave. These findings are consistent with Wijaya and Putri (2023), who reported that high job insecurity increases turnover intention, particularly in industries facing structural changes and policy uncertainty, and with Saputra et al. (2022), who found that job insecurity heightens stress and reduces commitment, thereby increasing turnover risk. However, other studies highlight moderating factors: Handayani and Prasetyo (2021) noted that not all employees experiencing job insecurity intend to leave, especially when alternatives are limited or incentives are provided, while Nugraha and Wahyuni (2022) observed that employees may remain despite high insecurity if supported by positive workplace relationships or perceived career opportunities within the organization. Overall, job insecurity directly contributes to turnover intention but its impact can be mitigated by organizational support, incentives, and strong interpersonal ties.

The Effect of Iconic Ethical Product on Purchase Decision

The results confirm that iconic ethical product has a significant positive effect on purchase decision, indicating that the stronger the ethnic uniqueness, symbolic value, and cultural identity embedded in Pamekasan batik, the higher the likelihood of consumers deciding to purchase it. Distinctive motifs, symbolic meanings rooted in local wisdom, unique ornaments, and functional comfort create perceptions of authenticity and value that foster consumer pride, trust, and emotional attachment. Descriptive analysis shows that both iconic ethical product and purchase decision are perceived positively, with motif appeal, symbolic appeal, ornamental appeal, and functional appeal emerging as the strongest indicators. These findings suggest that the ability of Pamekasan batik artisans to highlight ethnic characteristics differentiates their products from competitors and enhances market attractiveness. This result is consistent with Consumer Culture Theory, which emphasizes the role of symbolic meanings and cultural values in shaping consumer perceptions and purchasing behavior (Arnould et al., 2021), as well as prior studies indicating that ethnic and cultural attributes significantly influence purchase decisions for local cultural products (Herdiyanti et al., 2024; Silak et al., 2024).

The Effect of Product Innovation on Purchase Decision through Iconic Ethical Product

The fourth hypothesis is supported, indicating that product innovation positively influences purchase decision through iconic ethical product. This finding suggests that product innovation conducted by Pamekasan batik artisans becomes more effective in driving purchase decisions when it successfully strengthens ethnic uniqueness, cultural identity, and symbolic value embedded in the product. Consumers do not merely evaluate innovation in terms of novelty or technical improvement, but also consider the extent to which innovation reflects and reinforces local cultural values. Descriptive analysis shows that product innovation, iconic ethical product, and purchase decision are all perceived positively, supporting the mediating role of iconic ethical product. Consistent with Consumer Culture Theory, this result confirms that innovation affects purchase decisions indirectly through the construction of cultural and symbolic meanings (Arnould et al., 2021). Furthermore, this finding aligns with Yunitasari and Anwar (2022), who

emphasize that the combination of innovation and product uniqueness enhances market value. Overall, product innovation that is oriented toward strengthening iconic ethnical characteristics is more effective in increasing consumer interest and purchase decisions than innovation that is detached from ethnic identity.

V. CONCLUSION

CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis and discussion regarding the role of product innovation in influencing purchase decisions with iconic ethnical product as a mediating variable among Pamekasan batik consumers, this study concludes that product innovation plays an important role in strengthening the iconic and ethnic characteristics of Pamekasan batik by enriching its cultural identity rather than merely introducing design novelty. However, product innovation does not directly drive purchase decisions, as consumers place greater emphasis on symbolic value, cultural meaning, and ethnic identity embedded in the batik products. Furthermore, iconic ethnical product emerges as a central determinant of purchase decisions, as the attractiveness of motifs, symbols, colors, and ornaments representing local Pamekasan culture enhances consumer confidence and buying interest. Finally, the influence of product innovation on purchase decisions operates indirectly through the formation of iconic ethnical product, indicating that innovation becomes effective in encouraging purchases only when it successfully reinforces strong ethnic uniqueness and cultural symbolism. Overall, these findings highlight the crucial mediating role of iconic ethnical product in translating product innovation into consumer purchase decisions. concern.

SUGGESTION

Based on the findings of this study, batik artisans are encouraged to direct product innovation not merely toward design novelty, but toward strengthening local cultural identity by consistently preserving distinctive motifs, symbols, colors, and cultural philosophies of Pamekasan batik, so that the products maintain strong iconic and ethnic value in consumers' perceptions. Second, given that product innovation does not directly influence purchase decisions, artisans should align innovation efforts more closely with consumer perceptions and needs, supported by effective marketing communication strategies that clearly convey the symbolic and cultural meanings embedded in the products, allowing innovation to be perceived as added value rather than solely visual change. Third, considering the central role of iconic ethnical product in shaping purchase decisions, artisans should prioritize ethnic uniqueness as the core focus of product development and marketing strategies by consistently emphasizing cultural motifs, symbols, ornaments, and colors that represent Pamekasan's local identity. Finally, future studies are recommended to further examine specific forms of product innovation such as design innovation, motif development, and cultural meaning innovation that are most effective in strengthening iconic ethnical product characteristics, thereby enabling product innovation to exert a stronger and more direct influence on consumer purchase decisions.

REFERENCES

1. Al-Abdallah, G. M., & Al-Salim, M. I. (2021). Green product innovation and competitive advantage: An empirical study of chemical industrial plants in Jordanian qualified industrial zones. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, 28(8), 2542–2560.
2. Alamsyah, M. R., & Cahyono, K. E. (2021). Pengaruh kualitas produk, harga, promosi, dan citra merek terhadap keputusan pembelian pada Burger King Jemursari. *Jurnal Ilmu dan Riset Manajemen*, 10(6), 1–16.
3. Ardiansyah, F., & Nur, D. I. (2023). Penerapan digitalisasi UMKM sebagai upaya peningkatan kualitas pemasaran produk di Kelurahan Medokan Ayu. *JIPM: Jurnal Informasi Pengabdian Masyarakat*, 1(3).
4. Arnould, E., Crockett, D., & Eckhardt, G. (2021). Informing marketing theory through consumer culture theoretics. *AMS Review*, 11(1), 1–8.
5. Damayanti, V., & Zakik. (2023). Peranan industri batik dalam penyerapan tenaga kerja di Desa Klampar Kabupaten Pamekasan. *Buletin Ekonomika Pembangunan*, 4(2), 242–252.
6. Efendi, F. B., & Aminah, S. (2023). Pengaruh promosi dan kualitas produk terhadap keputusan pembelian produk skincare Skintific (Studi pada mahasiswa UPN "Veteran" Jawa Timur). *J-MAS (Jurnal Manajemen dan Sains)*, 8(1), 762–766.
7. Handayani, W., Winasih, S. S. Y., Fitriyah, Z., Dianty, S. A., Budi, A. S., & Hidayatullah, H. (2022). Inovasi produk limbah kain perca untuk mewujudkan green behavior warga Benowo Rejosari Pakal Surabaya. *Janaka: Jurnal Pengabdian Masyarakat*, 5(1), 34–43. <https://ejournal.staidapondokkrempyang.ac.id/index.php/janaka/article/view/153>

8. Herdiyanti, H., Launtu, A., Rahayu, B., Putra, S., & Anam, C. (2024). Analysis of the influence of cultural factors on consumer preferences in product purchasing decisions: A cross-cultural study of the global market. *Dinasti International Journal of Education Management and Social Science*, 5(5), 1384–1392.
9. Lee, J. W. (2024). Diffusion of innovations. In *Encyclopedia of sport management* (pp. 266–268). Edward Elgar Publishing.
10. Mardanugraha, E., & Junaidi, A. (2022). Ketahanan UMKM di Indonesia menghadapi resesi ekonomi. *Jurnal Ekonomi dan Pembangunan*, 30(2), 101–114.
11. Pakan, E. D., & Purwanto, S. (2022). Pengaruh beauty influencer dan kualitas produk terhadap keputusan pembelian produk facial wash Garnier di Surabaya. *Scientific Journal of Reflection: Economic, Accounting, Management and Business*, 5(3), 764–772.
12. Purwanto, S. (2017). Perilaku pembelian produk fashion didasarkan pada kepercayaan menggunakan media sosial. *Ekspektra: Jurnal Bisnis dan Manajemen*, 1(1), 55–67.
13. Ramadhani, M. F., & Raharjo, R. J. H. (2023). Pelatihan branding pada UMKM Desa Ngrimbi melalui pendekatan mentoring. *Jurnal Pengabdian Kepada Masyarakat Nusantara (JPkMN)*, 4(3), 2188–2195.
14. Soekesi, A. E. M., Purnamasari, S., & Elyadi, R. (2024). The influence of entrepreneurial characteristics, market orientation, product innovation, and entrepreneurial orientation on the business performance of SMEs.
15. Sulistiyani, S., & Hutomo, P. T. P. (2021). Model of product quality development on marketing performance in Semarang District. *South Asian Research Journal of Business and Management*, 3
16. Susanto, D. M., & Cahyono, K. E. (2021). Pengaruh citra merek, kualitas produk, dan harga terhadap keputusan pembelian iPhone (Studi pada mahasiswa di Surabaya). *Jurnal Ilmu dan Riset Manajemen*, 10(1).
17. Tjiptono, F. (2023). Riset pemasaran. Andi Offset.
18. Wang, Y. F., Lee, S. K., & Ye, Q. (2021). Opinion leaders in eco-innovation diffusion: Analysis of information networks for waste separation in Shanghai. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 174, 105822.
19. Yunitasari, S. S., & Anwar, M. (2022). Analisis keunikan produk dan inovasi produk terhadap kinerja pemasaran melalui keunggulan bersaing pada busana Muslim di Surabaya. *Widya Manajemen*, 4(2), 160–170.
20. Zghoul, H., & Al-Haddad, S. (2021). The influence of product innovation on customer satisfaction in the pharmaceutical sector in Jordan. *International Journal of Applied Research on Public Health Management (IJARPHM)*, 6(1), 45–63.

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